

Performance study and design of activated sludge reactor for treatment of dairy wastewater

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Manuscript received 15 November 2017, revised 23 February 2018, accepted 06 March 2018

Abstract : A laboratory scale investigation was done in order to evaluate the kinetic constants for design of an activated sludge process for treatment of dairy wastewater in field scale. The effluent was collected from various points of existing effluent treatment plant (ETP) unit of a local milk processing industry and subsequently its characteristics were evaluated. A simulated sample on the basis of statistically derived real life effluent characteristics was prepared synthetically with an average COD concentration of 700 mg/L. Microbial seed was acclimatized in the laboratory which was used for subsequent phases of batch study. Organic removal as of COD, MLSS and pH variation with time were also observed during the process keeping an initial biomass concentration of 1200 mg/L for a constant period of 2 days. Kinetic constants were obtained as yield coefficient (Y) = 0.429 mg COD/mg MLSS, half velocity constant (K_s) = 171.69 mg/L, endogenous decay constant (k_d) = 0.065 d⁻¹ and substrate removal rate coefficient (k) = 13.33 d⁻¹.

Keywords : Activated sludge process, kinetic constants, COD removal, dairy wastewater.

I. Introduction

Wastewater generated from agro-industries has distinctive characteristics that set it apart from general municipal and other typical industrial wastewaters¹. In many countries, dairy industry is considered to be one of the largest source of food-processing wastewater. In general, dairy industry generates about 0.2–10 L of effluent/L of processed milk². It is stated that for Indian dairy industries, maximum allowable wastewater generation is limited to 3 m³/KL of milk processed (The Environmental (Protection) Rules, 1986) which indicates that for every L of milk to be processed, the volume of wastewater generated should be kept below 3 L. Wastewater from dairy industry contains highly putrescent constituents that in shortage of oxygen generates foul

smell and undesirable gases. The high organic load, when degrades rapidly, deplete the DO (dissolved oxygen) level of the receiving streams. Dairy effluents contain dissolved sugars and proteins, fats and possibly residues of additives which are the main contributors to the organic load of these waste waters. Analysis of raw and treated effluent from a local dairy industry showed the raw wastewater had COD and BOD concentrations of 1000 and 785 mg/L. The treated effluent after undergoing primary sedimentation and activated sludge processes had a COD of 275 mg/L and BOD of 58.0 mg/L which was not within the safe limits and most of the times the effluent was released in local environment. These small scale local dairy industries are quite common in rural and suburban areas of India. Keeping the prob-

lem exists in environmental sector, the present study was undertaken to evaluate kinetic parameters by activated sludge batch process and develop approximate design parameters for the reactor involved. From the works of earlier researchers³⁻⁵ a series of removal efficiencies in terms of BOD, COD, SS by continuous activated sludge processes is obtained for medium to large scale dairy units. The objective of the present work was to evaluate the kinetic coefficients for treating a small scale dairy wastewater from laboratory batch studies for designing an activated sludge reactor and to compare results obtained by earlier researchers.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

For the analysis of chemical oxygen demand (COD) of dairy effluent as per standard guidelines prescribed by APHA⁶, 1999, (N/4) potassium dichromate [$K_2Cr_2O_7$], (N/10) Mohr's salt, conc. sulfuric acid [H_2SO_4], silver sulfate [Ag_2SO_4], mercuric sulfate [$HgSO_4$] and ferroin indicator was required. The reagents of required strength was prepared as per IS 2316 : 1990.

B. Preparation of synthetic sample

The present study was carried out using simulated dairy wastewater sample having its COD concentration similar to that of a small scale dairy industry. Samples from a local small scale dairy processing unit were collected at regular intervals to establish statistically mean values of raw wastewater characteristics. The simulated sample was prepared synthetically on the basis of statistically derived real life effluent characteristic with average initial COD concentration of 700 mg/L. The synthetic sample was prepared by dissolving the following chemicals

in particular proportions in 1 L of the sample (Table 1) and diluting it four times.

Table 1. The composition of stock synthetic sample

Sl. No.	Constituent	Amount (in g)
1.	Milk powder	1.0
2.	Dextrose	1.0
3.	Peptone	0.5
4.	Beef extract	0.25
	Yeast extract	
5.	Lactose	0.25
6.	K_2HPO_4	0.20
7.	KH_2PO_4	0.25
8.	Sludge collected	0.5
Sodium bicarbonate for pH adjustment (6.5–7.5).		

C. Analytical method

In the present study, the different analytical tests carried out are listed in Table 2. The respective methods for the analytical experiments are followed accordingly as mentioned.

D. Experimental studies

The study was carried out in a laboratory scale activated sludge reactor setup at the School of Environmental Studies Laboratory, Jadavpur University, Kolkata. In the laboratory, a setup comprising of an aeration tank and a sedimentation tank was installed. The aeration tank having a total volume of 46.648 L (490 mm × 340 mm × 280 mm) and a working volume of 20 L is fitted with a compressor for supplying air at a rate of 8 L/min with perforated flexible pipes placed at the bottom of the tank. Samples were withdrawn from the tank by means of an auto-pipette. Since the reactor is operated as a batch process, arrangements for constant inflow and outflow are not required. The setup is shown in Fig. 1 along with its corresponding schematic diagram in Fig. 2.

Table 2. List of different analytical experiments carried out in the study and the corresponding methods followed

Sl. No.	Parameters	Analytical methods followed	Guidelines followed
1.	pH	Electrometric method (pH meter)	APHA methods ⁷ , Part 4500 H, 18th ed., 1992
2.	COD	Open reflux method	APHA methods ⁶ , Part 5220, 20th ed., 1999
3.	MLSS	Gravimetric method (103–105°C)	APHA methods ⁶ , Part 2540, 20th ed., 1999
4.	BOD	5 days BOD by DO determination	APHA methods ⁶ , Part 5210 B, 20th ed., 1999

Fig. 1. Lab scale activated sludge reactor in working condition.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of lab scale activated sludge reactor.

The study was overall carried out in batch processes as batch reactors are simpler to operate and problems and interferences inherently associated with reactor hydraulics are avoided⁸. These units work well for dairy plants that confine their operations to an 8 to 10 h workday⁹.

The study was carried out with an initial COD concentration of around 700 mg/L and an initial biomass concentration of 1200 mg/L using the lab scale ASP reactor in batch process over a period of 48 h.

The operating condition for the study is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Operating conditions for lab scale reactor

Sl. No.	Parameters	Range
1.	Temperature	27–32°C
2.	Air supply rate	8 L/min
3.	pH	7.60–7.90
4.	COD (mg/L)	680–722
5.	BOD (mg/L)	494–531

The kinetic coefficients were determined along with a time concentration profile study for pH, MLSS and % COD removal allowing a retention time varying from 2 to 48 h with initial biomass concentration of 1200 mg/L. For determination of kinetic coefficients, samples having an initial COD concentration around 700 mg/L were withdrawn at different retention times varying from 2 to 48 h using different initial biomass concentrations to determine the residual organics (in terms of COD) in the sample. Kinetics parameters (such as S_0 , S and X) are evaluated from bench scale study for different HRTs.

The kinetic coefficients for activated sludge process are determined following Burk-Lineweaver model using the eqs. (1) and (2) :

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{K_s}{k} \frac{1}{S} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (1)$$

Now, plotting a graph with $1/U$ in the Y-axis and $1/S$ in the X-axis will help to determine the values of the two important kinetic parameters K_0 and K_s . Here,

the value of $\frac{S_0 - S}{X\theta_c}$ is represented as U , known as specific substrate utilization ratio.

To find the value of Y and k_d the following equation can be used to plot a graph

$$\frac{1}{\theta_c} = \frac{S_0 - S}{X\theta_c} Y - k_d \quad (2)$$

The graph is plotted by taking $1/\theta_c$ in the Y-axis and $\frac{S_0 - S}{X\theta_c}$ in the X-axis to find the values of Y and k_d .

k_d is the intercept of the Y-axis and the slope of the graph gives the value of Y .

III. Results and discussion

A. Time profile of pH, MLSS, COD concentration and residual COD over 48 h

The gradual change of pH in the reactor was monitored for 2 to 48 h using an initial MLSS concentration of 1200 mg/L and initial COD concentration of around 700 mg/L. The time concentration profile is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Time concentration profile for pH, MLSS variation and COD reduction.

The pH, initially was chosen in the range of 7.05 to 7.3. Neutral to slightly alkaline pH is suitable for the activity of microorganisms in activated sludge process¹⁰. The steep increase in pH values in the first few hours is because free CO_2 may combine with CO_3^{2-} ion to produce bicarbonate alkalinity (HCO_3^-). Later on, buffering capacity of the process reduces pH followed by more CO_2 production. After 30 h, the marginal increment of pH is perhaps due to nitrification activity of the biomass¹¹.

From Fig. 3, it is observed that there is a steady increase in MLSS level in the batch reactor starting from the commencement of the contact period. The rate of increase of MLSS was found to be high initially as food to microorganism ratio (F/M) was high predominantly. As the reaction proceeds, the available substrate in soluble form decreases and thus,

growth rate decreases. Again in between 18 to 24 h, there is an increase in growth rate, because of endogenous degradation of bacteria present in the reactor. Thereafter, the rate of growth is low. MLSS concentration is thus, a control variable and not a response variable¹². Initial MLSS concentration was taken 1200 mg/L which increased by 120.3% after 48 h.

Using an initial MLSS concentration of 1200 mg/L, the study was carried out in lab-scale reactor with an initial COD concentration of around 700 mg/L. During the initial biological uptake of the organic material, more than half of it is oxidized and the remainder is assimilated as new biomass, which may be further oxidized by endogenous respiration¹⁰. The Figure shows that an identical pattern of COD removal is appeared as first order reaction. COD is removed sharply within the first 24 h, thereafter the rate of removal decreases. The treatment can be said to be completed in two major phases. During the first, or assimilation, phase, sludge bacteria rapidly consumed the food in the milk waste and required oxygen at a high rate¹³. During the second, or endogenous, phase, because these bacteria received no new food supply, they underwent endogenous metabolism¹⁴ and so after a slow rate of change of MLSS concentration, the growth rate is seen to be increased for a short span of time. At 48 h, the removal of COD was maximum; beyond the period removal is marginal, though a constant cessation was not achieved because the test was not continued beyond 48 h. % COD removal corresponding to 48 h was observed to be nearly 73%.

B. Kinetic coefficients

Based on kinetic studies carried out in these conditions, kinetic coefficients for activated sludge process are determined following Burk-Lineweaver model using eqs. (1) and (2).

Plotting the data obtained during the study in eq. (2), the graph between U vs $(1/\theta_c)$ is obtained. Fig. 4 gives the magnitude of yield coefficient (Y) as 0.429 mg MLSS/mg COD and decay coefficient (k_d) as 0.065 d^{-1} .

Fig. 4. Determination of Y and k_d .

The graph from eq. (1) yields the values of half velocity constant (K_s) as 171.69 mg/L and substrate removal rate coefficient (k) as 13.33 d^{-1} .

Fig. 5. Determination of K_s and k .

For a specified waste, a given biological community and a particular set of environmental conditions, the kinetic coefficients have a fixed value¹⁰. Each of the coefficients is important for determining the optimum pertaining condition and size of the reactor. The kinetic coefficient values used to predict the design of an activated sludge reactor vary as a function of wastewater source, microbial population and temperature. Experimental conditions and the kinetic coefficients obtained by previous researchers working on dairy wastewater by activated sludge processes are shown in Table 4a and Table 4b, respectively.

Table 4a. Experimental conditions of the studies for determination of kinetic coefficients performed by previous researchers

Authors	Experimental conditions
Present study	(i) Temperature : 27–320°C (ii) Air supply rate : 8 L/min (iii) pH : 7.60–7.90 (iv) COD (mg/L) : 680–722 (v) BOD (mg/L) : 494–531
Venkatesan <i>et al.</i> (2004) (Ref. 3)	Studies were carried out in a bench-scale continuous flow stirred tank reactor without recycle (i) Capacity of the tank : 9 L (ii) DO level : more than 3 mg/L (iii) Initial MLSS concentration : 772–1386 mg/L (iv) Initial BOD concentration : 1100–1146 mg/L
Lateef <i>et al.</i> (2013) (Ref. 5)	Studies were performed in a completely mixed continuous reactor without recycle (i) Working volume of aeration tank : 25.45 L (ii) Temperature during study period : 16–24°C (iii) pH range : 7.0 to 8.0 (iv) DO level : 3 to 4.2 mg/L (v) Average initial BOD (as substrate) : 1520 mg/L (vi) Initial MLSS concentration : 569–848 mg/L
Carta-Escobar <i>et al.</i> (2005) (Ref. 4)	Results were obtained from studies in a series three reactor system (i) pH : 11 (ii) Initial COD concentration : 4000 mg/L (iii) Temperature : 300°C (iv) Volumetric organic loading : 0.237–0.7 kg COD/m ³ d

Since the values of these coefficients are dependent on environmental as well as working conditions, the data varies with the works of different researchers. The values of these kinetic coefficients are also observed to vary inversely with the hydraulic retention time¹⁵.

Table 4b. Kinetic coefficients evaluated by previous researchers

Authors	Cell yield coefficient (Y)	Decay coefficient (k_d, d^{-1})	Maximum substrate utilization rate (k, d^{-1})	Half velocity constant, K_s mg/L
Present study	0.429	0.065	13.33	171.69
Venkatesan <i>et al.</i> (2004) (Ref. 3)	0.933	0.015	2.5	867.76
Lateef <i>et al.</i> (2013) (Ref. 5)	0.714	0.038	4.46	534
Carta-Escobar <i>et al.</i> (2005) (Ref. 4)	0.26	0.032	–	141

The value of yield (Y) is virtually constant for a wide variety of substrate treated aerobically and it gives an idea of quantity of sludge produced. The greater the value of Y , the greater will be the amount of sludge production and so the size of sludge handling facility and thus the cost will increase³. Biomass growth rate is proportional to the substrate utilization rate by yield coefficient. Higher Y values also suggest better rate of reaction.

Higher value of k_d reduces the net production of sludge.

The value of K_s illustrates the specific growth rate of bacteria with variation of substrate concentration.

The magnitude of k affects the volume of the reactor and is inversely proportional with the later¹⁶.

IV. Conclusion

Laboratory test results showed that dairy wastewater is favourably degradable for organic load removal of COD in batch aeration unit. More than 70% removal was obtained for a retention time of 48 h using initial COD concentration of 700 mg/L for MLSS concentration of 1200 mg/L. The kinetic constants are reasonably corroborated with standard values and the same was used for design of aeration tank system in an activated sludge treatment of dairy plant. These kinetic values will be useful for design of such unit in the country.

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